

Oxalatofluorotitanates

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The preparation of $K_4[Ti_2O(C_2O_4)_3F_4] \cdot 2.5H_2O$ and $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2F_2] \cdot 3H_2O$ are described. The compounds are studied through TGA, i.r. spectra and through X-ray analysis.

The conductometric and thermometric titrations of potassium titanyl oxalate by KF, AgF and by HF indicate the formation of the ion, $[TiO(C_2O_4)_2F_2]^{2-}$ in aqueous solution.

MANY oxalatotitanates are reported¹⁻⁶ in the literature but very little is known about oxalatofluorotitanates. Guerchais⁷ reported (details unpublished) the presence of the species of the type, $[Ti_2F_8(C_2O_4)_3]^{2-}$ and $[TiF_4(C_2O_4)]^{2-}$. He studied the structural aspects of the above ions from ¹⁹F NMR study in solution. In the present work, two new compounds, $K_4[Ti_2O(C_2O_4)_3F_4] \cdot 2.5H_2O$ and $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2F_2] \cdot 3H_2O$ are reported. These compounds are studied through TGA, i.r. spectroscopy and X-ray analysis.

Moreover, the formation of oxalatofluorotitanate ions in solution was studied through conductometric and thermometric titrations of potassium titanyl oxalate by KF, HF and by AgF.

Experimental

The chemicals used in the present work were of reagent quality. Potassium titanyl oxalate, $K_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ and hexamminecobalt(III) nitrate were prepared by standard methods^{8,9}. Potassium was estimated as sulphate after prior separation of titanium. Titanium was estimated as TiO_2 through standard procedures. Cobalt was estimated by electrogravimetric method after separation of titanium as cupferronate. Fluorine was analysed gravimetrically as $PbClF$ and nitrogen by semimicro Dumas' method. Oxalate was estimated permanganometrically in presence of boric acid (1-2 g).

Conductometric and thermometric titrations of potassium titanyl oxalate :

For each titration fresh solution was made by dissolving potassium titanyloxalate of known weight dissolved in known volume of carbon dioxide-free conductivity water. HF was standardised by titrating with caustic soda using phenolphthalein as indicator. For the preparation of standard KF solution, fluorine was estimated from it gravimetrically. Standard AgF was prepared by dissolving hydrated silver oxide in minimum volume of HF in such a manner that a little amount of silver oxide was left undissolved. The precipitate was filtered

and silver and fluorine was estimated. Silver oxide was obtained as a precipitate from the reaction of $AgNO_3$ solution with caustic alkali. Excess of alkali was removed on washing with distilled water. The fluoride and HF solutions were preserved in polythene bottles. Calibrated polythene burette and pipette were used.

The conductance of the solutions were measured with a Phillips Conductivity Bridge No. PR 9500. A conductivity cell containing dip type platinum electrodes fitted in polythene stems was used. For each of the conductometric titration system consisting of potassium titanyl oxalate and fluorides/HF, three titrations were performed, viz., (a) a known volume (x ml) of standard potassium titanyl oxalate was titrated conductometrically by water (conductance values denoted as X), (b) a known volume (x ml) of water was titrated conductometrically (conductance values denoted as Y) by standard HF or KF or AgF and (c) a known volume (x ml) of potassium titanyl oxalate was titrated conductometrically (conductance of mixtures denoted as Z) by the same HF or KF or AgF that was used in the above titration. The difference of the conductance values (X+Y-Z) was plotted against molar ratio $[HF \text{ or } MF]/[K_2TiO(C_2O_4)_2]$, where M = K^+ or Ag^+ and the results are reported in Figures 1, 2 and 3.

A thermometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate by HF was carried out as before¹⁰ and temperature change at constant volume (T_v) was plotted (Fig. 4) against the molar ratio $[HF]/[K_2TiO(C_2O_4)_2]$.

Preparation of oxalatofluorotitanates :

(1) $K_4[Ti_2O(C_2O_4)_3F_4] \cdot 2.5H_2O$: Potassium titanyl oxalate (3.54 g) was dissolved in water (50 ml) and was mixed with potassium fluoride (1.16 g) also dissolved in water (10 ml). The pH of the mixture was lowered from 4.24 to 3.04 by adding 25 ml glacial acetic acid. The mixture was crystallised in a desiccator containing conc. H_2SO_4 . The crystals were filtered, washed once with cold

Fig. 1. Conductometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate by KF at 30°.

Curve I. X represents the conductance recorded in the blank titration of 35 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.01 M) by water; Y represents the conductance recorded in the blank titration of 35 ml water by KF (0.25 M); Z denotes the conductance recorded in the titration of 35 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.01 M) by KF (0.25 M).

Curve II. X, Y and Z have the same significance as above in the titration of 35 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.001 M) by KF (0.025 M).

Fig. 3. Conductometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate by HF at 30°.

Curve I. X represents the conductance recorded in the blank titration of 35 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.001 M) by water; Y denotes the conductance recorded in the blank titration of 35 ml water by HF (0.02 M); Z represents the conductance recorded in the titration of 35 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.001 M) by HF (0.02 M).

Curve II. Y and Z have the same significance as above in the titration of 75 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.001 M) by HF (0.10 M). X denotes the conductance of 75 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.001 M).

Fig. 2. Conductometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate by AgF at 30°.

Curve I. X represents the conductance recorded in the blank titration of 35 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.01 M) by AgF (0.25 M); Y represents the conductance recorded in the blank titration of 35 ml water by AgF (0.25 M); Z denotes the conductance recorded in the titration of 35 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.01 M) by AgF (0.25 M).

Curve II. X, Y and Z have the same significance as above in the titration of 35 ml potassium titanyl oxalate (0.005 M) by AgF (0.125 M).

Fig. 4. Curve I. Thermometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate (0.2 M) by HF (10 M).

Curve II. Thermometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate (0.1 M) by HF (5 M).

water, pressed between the filter paper, and dried first in a desiccator containing KOH and then in air to constant weight.

Anal. Calcd: K, 23.94; Ti, 14.67; Oxalate, 40.42; F, 11.63%.

Found: K, 24.74; Ti, 14.46; Oxalate, 40.34; F, 11.89%.

(2) $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2F_2]_3 \cdot 3H_2O$: Potassium titanyl oxalate (1.50 g) was dissolved in water (25 ml) and 12.75 ml. AgF (0.6643 M) was added with stirring in the ratio of $K_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2]/AgF = 1/2$. The solution was filtered and to it hexamminecobalt(III) nitrate (0.88 g) dissolved in water (40 ml) was added, when precipitation took place immediately. The precipitate was filtered, washed once with cold water and then with rectified spirit. The compound was dried in air. The reaction can be represented as,

Anal. Calcd. : Co, 12.46 ; N, 17.77 ; Ti, 15.20 ; Oxalate, 27.93 ; F, 12.06%.

Found Co, 12.35 ; N, 17.21 ; Ti, 14.89 ; Oxalate, 28.00 ; F, 12.00%.

$K_4[Ti_2O(C_2O_4)_3F_4] \cdot 2.5H_2O$ is white in colour. It could not be recrystallised from water. The hexamminecobalt(III) compound is light yellow and insoluble in water. Both the compounds are insoluble in common organic solvents. On drying over P_2O_5 in vacuum at room temperature both the compounds lose water molecules giving the corresponding anhydrous compounds.

Thermogravimetric studies : The data were recorded in a manually operated thermobalance. The heating rate for the compound, $K_4[Ti_2O(C_2O_4)_3F_4] \cdot 2.5H_2O$ was 2°/minute and that of $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2F_2]_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ was 5°/minute (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5.

Infrared spectra : The data were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer apparatus in KBr pallets in the range 400-4000 cm^{-1} (Table 1).

X-ray studies : The X-ray powder diffraction data of $K_4[Ti_2O(C_2O_4)_3F_4] \cdot 2.5H_2O$ were recorded in a G.E.C. diffractometer using $Cu K_{\alpha}$ radiations (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titrations of potassium titanyl oxalate by KF (Fig. 1) show breaks corres-

TABLE-1 INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA

I	II	Probable band assignment (cm^{-1})
450-600(S, b)	500-600(S, b)	$\nu(Ti-F)$, $\nu(Ti-O)$, $\nu(C-C)$
800(S)	715(vw)	$\delta(O-C-O)$, $\nu(Ti-O)$
	800(S)	
	850(Sh)	
	900(Sh)	
1260(m)	1250(S)	$\nu(O-C-O) + \delta(O-C-O)$
1325(m)		
1350(Sh)		$\delta(NH_3)$
1400(S)	1400(S)	$\nu(O-C-O) + \nu(C-C)$
1685(S)	1690(S)} _d	$\nu_{as}(O-C-O)$, $\delta(NH_3)$, HOH
	1725(S)} _d	
	2920(vw)	
3100-3340(b)		νOH , $\nu(NH_3)$
3400-3600(w, b)	3450} _d	
	3580} _d	

I. $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2F_2]_3 \cdot 3H_2O$

II. $K_4[Ti_2O(C_2O_4)_3F_4] \cdot 2.5H_2O$

S=sharp, m=medium, w=weak, vw=very weak, b=broad, d=doublet and Sh=shoulder.

TABLE-2 X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA

dA	Relative Intensity	dA	Relative Intensity
5.64	W	3.42	M
5.08	W	3.23	W
4.74	W	3.14	VW
3.86	VW	3.04	M
3.67	M	2.71	S
3.46	W	2.68	VS
		2.18	S

VS=Very sharp, S=Sharp, M=Medium, W=Weak, VW=Very weak.

ponding to the reaction ratio, $[TiO(C_2O_4)_2]^{2-} : KF$ at 1 : 2 whereas conductometric titrations of potassium titanyl oxalate by AgF (Fig. 2) show breaks at 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 also. The probable general equation at the ratio, $[TiO(C_2O_4)_2]^{2-} : MF$ (where $M = K^+$ or Ag^+) = 1 : 2 may be represented as :

The break at 1 : 4 in the conductometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate by AgF is probably due to the reaction :

The above explanations are also supported from the thermometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate by HF as shown below.

The thermometric titrations of potassium titanyl oxalate by HF (Fig. 4) show two breaks at the ratios 1 : 2 and 1 : 4. Besides, fine crystals of oxalic acid were found to be present in the reaction vessel at the end of the titration. The conductometric titration of potassium titanyl oxalate by HF (Fig. 3) also suggests the generation of stronger acid through the reaction. These reactions may be represented

as :

The thermal decomposition study of potassium oxalate and sodium oxalate by different workers^{11,12} suggested that these compounds become anhydrous by losing water of crystallisation at first and then formation of carbonates take place through the evolution of CO. But the pyrolysis curve of $\text{K}_4[\text{Ti}_2\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3\text{F}_4] \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows gradual loss in weight with rise in temperature. The curve does not show any horizontal stretch whatsoever, corresponding to the loss of water of crystallisation. The compound was found to be thermally stable up to 50°.

The thermogram of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)\text{F}_2]_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicates that the compound is stable up to 50°. The decomposition is quite rapid from 220° to 340°. The thermogram does not show any intermediate compound formation, not even the formation of anhydrous compound. The residue obtained at the constant weight (at 360°) was found to be the oxides of cobalt and titanium (loss in weight : Calcd : 66.09% ($\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4 + \text{TiO}_2$); Found : 63.90%). The thermogram of anhydrous $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)\text{F}_2]_3$ does not show any remarkable difference from that of the hydrated one.

The infrared spectra of the compounds show that the oxalate groups present in the compounds are most probably acting as chelating ligands^{13,14}. From the i.r. spectrum of $\text{K}_4[\text{Ti}_2\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3\text{F}_4] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, it could not be ascertained whether any of the three oxalate groups is acting as a bridge between two titanium atoms.

The Ti-F bands occur in the region of 500-650 cm^{-1} ¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Both the compounds show broad bands at 450-600 cm^{-1} which may be attributed to Ti-F stretching mode. But chelate oxalate compounds also show a band at 520-570 cm^{-1} which has been assigned to M-O and C-C stretching frequencies. Thus the superimposition of these bands on one another is not unlikely. Similarly superimposition of O-C-O deformation band on Ti-O band¹⁹⁻²² is possible around 800 cm^{-1} which usually occur respectively at 800 cm^{-1} and 800-900 cm^{-1} . Besides, the i.r. spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)\text{F}_2]_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ show typical frequencies of N-H at 3000-3400 cm^{-1} , 1550-1650 cm^{-1} and 1400-1470 cm^{-1} , etc.

The absorption in the region 3200-3550 cm^{-1} due to antisymmetric and symmetric OH stretching are observed in both the compounds, but the band at 1600-1630 cm^{-1} due to HOH bending²³ could not be identified probably due to the superimposition of the band with (O-C-O) asymmetric stretching.

The d-values of the compound, $\text{K}_4[\text{Ti}_2\text{O}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3\text{F}_4] \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are compared with those of the compounds, $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and KHC_2O_4 and it was found to be free from them.

The purity of the compound, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)\text{F}_2]_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ could not be ascertained from X-ray diffraction patterns due to the limited scope of the laboratory. In the case of this compound two things might happen, viz., (i) the reaction of potassium titanyl oxalate may take place in 1 : 4 ratio instead of 1 : 2 leaving behind half the total amount of potassium titanyl oxalate unreacted and the reaction of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6](\text{NO}_3)_3$ with unreacted half will give $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]_3$ and (ii) there must be simultaneous formation of the compound $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiOF}_4]_3$. But it was seen that the conductometric-titrations of potassium titanyl oxalate with AgF show distinct breaks at 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 ratio, probably indicating the stepwise removal of two oxalate ions. It was also seen that the reaction of the solution, obtained through the complete removal of oxalate ions by AgF in 1 : 4 ratio, with hexamminecobalt(III) chloride did not yield a pure compound of the type, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiOF}_4]_3$. From these considerations it may be concluded that the compound, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)\text{F}_2]_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is not a mixture of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]_3$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiOF}_4]_3$ in 1 : 1 ratio.

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